

ISic1268

I.Sicily inscription 1268

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140757

1. [— — — — —]Α ἔζη
2. [— — — — —]Ι □ XXX
3. [χαῖρε καὶ] σὺ.
- 4.
5. [— —]ΛΒΙΟ [— —]
6. [— —]ΥΗΤ [— —]
7. [— — —]. [— —]
- 8.
9. ἀνε [παύσατο — —]
10. ΑΦΡ [— — — — —]
11. τελ ε [υτησ— — —]
12. κίτε Ι [— — — — —]
- 13.
14. [— —]ΙΑCT̄#⁷ [— —]
15. [— —] ἔζησε υ [— —]
- 16.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644961

PHI 140757

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0443.1-4 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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